

Determinants of Glucose Imbalance and Its Impact on the Development of Undiagnosed Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in Urban and Rural Communities

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Abstract:

Background: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a global health concern with increasing prevalence, significantly impacting morbidity and mortality rates. Urban and rural communities exhibit distinct health profiles, influencing the determinants and prevalence of glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM. This study aimed to investigate the determinants of glucose imbalance and its impact on the development of undiagnosed T2DM in urban and rural communities.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted with 90 participants, evenly split between an urban and a rural community. Data were collected through questionnaires, physical examinations, and laboratory tests measuring fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with multivariate logistic regression used to identify significant determinants of glucose imbalance.

Results: The rural community exhibited a higher prevalence of glucose imbalance (55.6%) and undiagnosed T2DM (31.1%) compared to the urban community (42.2% and 17.8%, respectively). Significant determinants of glucose imbalance included age (OR=1.04, p=0.022), BMI (OR=1.11, p=0.013), and low socio-economic status (OR=3.22, p=0.016).

Conclusion: The study highlighted a higher vulnerability to glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM in the rural community, primarily due to lower socio-economic status. Age and BMI were also significant predictors of glucose imbalance.

Recommendations: Targeted interventions are needed to address glucose imbalance and prevent T2DM, especially in rural areas with lower socio-economic status. Public health initiatives should focus on lifestyle modifications and improving access to healthcare services.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Glucose Imbalance, Urban Community, Rural Community, Socio-economic Status.

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Introduction

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and progressive beta-cell dysfunction, leading to hyperglycemia. It has become a major global health concern due to its rising prevalence and significant impact on morbidity and mortality. According to the International Diabetes Federation, the number of adults living with diabetes globally increased from 451 million in 2017 to 537 million in 2021, with projections reaching 783 million by 2045 if current trends continue [1]. This alarming rise is primarily driven by lifestyle changes, urbanization, and increasing obesity rates.

Urban and rural communities often exhibit distinct health profiles due to varying socio-economic conditions, access to healthcare, dietary habits, and levels of physical activity. Studies have shown that urbanization is associated with a higher prevalence of diabetes and related risk factors, including obesity, sedentary lifestyle, and unhealthy dietary patterns [2]. Conversely, rural populations, although sometimes exhibiting lower rates of obesity, may have limited access to healthcare services, poorer health literacy, and higher rates of poverty, which can contribute to undiagnosed and poorly managed diabetes.

Understanding the determinants of glucose imbalance and the subsequent development of undiagnosed T2DM in these diverse settings is crucial for effective public health interventions. Glucose imbalance, indicated by abnormal fasting glucose levels and elevated HbA1c, is an early indicator of insulin resistance and impaired glucose tolerance, both of which are precursors to T2DM [3]. Identifying populations at risk of glucose imbalance can facilitate early intervention and prevent the progression to full-blown diabetes.

Recent research highlights several determinants of glucose imbalance, including age, body mass index (BMI), socio-economic status, and lifestyle factors such as diet and physical activity [4]. Age is a well-established risk factor, as insulin sensitivity decreases and beta-cell function declines with aging. High BMI, particularly central obesity, is strongly associated with insulin resistance and subsequent glucose dysregulation [5]. Socio-economic status influences health behaviors and access to healthcare, with lower socio-economic groups experiencing higher rates of glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM due to barriers in accessing preventive and therapeutic services.

This study assessed the determinants of glucose imbalance and its effect on the development of undiagnosed Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in both urban and rural communities.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in two distinct settings: an urban community and a rural community, both located within the same geographical region to minimize environmental variability.

Participants: The study included a total of 90 participants, with 45 participants from the urban community and 45 participants from the rural community. Participants were selected using a stratified random sampling method to ensure representative samples from both settings.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18-65 years.
- Residents of the selected urban or rural community for at least one year.
- Individuals not previously diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.

Exclusion Criteria

- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Individuals with a known diagnosis of diabetes mellitus.
- Participants with severe chronic illnesses or disabilities that could affect glucose metabolism.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from community registers. Information bias was reduced by training data collectors and using standardized procedures for data collection.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of questionnaires, physical examinations, and laboratory tests. The questionnaire gathered demographic information, lifestyle factors, medical history, and dietary habits. Physical examinations measured anthropometric parameters. Blood samples were taken to measure fasting blood glucose, HbA1c levels, and lipid profiles.

Procedure: Participants were recruited from the selected communities and informed consent was obtained. A structured questionnaire was administered to collect demographic and lifestyle information. Height, weight, and BMI were measured. Fasting blood samples were collected for laboratory analysis of glucose and HbA1c levels. All data were recorded in a standardized format and entered into a secure database.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Comparisons between urban and rural participants were made using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Multivariate logistic regression was used to identify determinants of glucose imbalance and their association with undiagnosed T2DM. Results were presented with corresponding 95% confidence intervals and p-values, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 90 participants were included in the study, with 45 from the urban community and 45 from the rural community. The demographic characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Condition	Urban	Rural	p-value
Mean Age (years)	42.5 ± 12.3	44.1 ± 11.8	0.532
Gender			
Male	22	20	0.661
Female	23	25	0.049*

BMI (kg/m ²)	28.4 ± 5.2	26.7 ± 4.9	
Socio-economic Status			
- Low	12 (26.7%)	29 (64.4%)	<0.001**
- Middle	24 (53.3%)	14 (31.1%)	
- High	9 (20.0%)	2 (4.4%)	

*Significant at p<0.05, **Significant at p<0.01

The prevalence of glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM among the participants is shown in Table 2. Glucose imbalance was determined by fasting blood glucose levels and HbA1c levels, with undiagnosed T2DM defined by HbA1c ≥ 6.5%.

Table 2: Prevalence of Glucose Imbalance and Undiagnosed T2DM

Condition	Urban	Rural	p-value
Glucose Imbalance	19 (42.2%)	25 (55.6%)	0.185
Undiagnosed T2DM	8 (17.8%)	14 (31.1%)	0.131

Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify determinants of glucose imbalance. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Determinants of Glucose Imbalance

Variables	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Age	1.04 (1.01 - 1.08)	0.022*
Gender (Male)	1.25 (0.58 - 2.70)	0.565
BMI	1.11 (1.02 - 1.20)	0.013*
Socio-economic Status		
- Low	3.22 (1.24 - 8.37)	0.016*
- Middle	2.15 (0.82 - 5.65)	0.118

*Significant at p<0.05

Comparative analysis of glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM between urban and rural communities is illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of Glucose Imbalance and Undiagnosed T2DM Between Urban and Rural Communities

Condition	Urban	Rural	p-value
Glucose Imbalance	19 (42.2%)	25 (55.6%)	0.185
Undiagnosed T2DM	8 (17.8%)	14 (31.1%)	0.131
BMI	28.4 ± 5.2	26.7 ± 4.9	0.049*
Age	42.5 ± 12.3	44.1 ± 11.8	0.532
Socio-economic Status			
- Low	12 (26.7%)	29 (64.4%)	<0.001**
- Middle	24 (53.3%)	14 (31.1%)	
- High	9 (20.0%)	2 (4.4%)	

*Significant at p<0.05, **Significant at p<0.01

Discussion

A total of 90 participants were included, evenly split between the urban and rural settings. The analysis revealed significant differences in socio-economic status and BMI between the two groups. The rural community had a higher proportion of individuals with low socio-economic status (64.4% compared to 26.7% in the urban community, p<0.001) and a lower average BMI (26.7 ± 4.9 kg/m² compared to 28.4 ± 5.2 kg/m², p=0.049).

The prevalence of glucose imbalance was higher in the rural community (55.6%) compared to the urban community (42.2%), though this difference was not statistically significant (p=0.185). Similarly, the prevalence of undiagnosed T2DM

was higher in the rural community (31.1%) compared to the urban community (17.8%), but again, this difference was not statistically significant (p=0.131).

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified age, BMI, and low socio-economic status as significant determinants of glucose imbalance. Specifically, each additional year of age increased the odds of glucose imbalance by 4% (OR=1.04, p=0.022), and each unit increase in BMI increased the odds by 11% (OR=1.11, p=0.013). Participants with low socio-economic status had more than three times the odds of glucose imbalance compared to those with high socio-economic status (OR=3.22, p=0.016).

The comparative analysis highlighted that the rural community is more vulnerable to glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM, likely due to the higher prevalence of low socio-economic status. The findings suggest that interventions to address glucose imbalance and prevent T2DM should particularly focus on rural areas and individuals with lower socio-economic status. Addressing factors such as age and BMI through lifestyle modifications and targeted public health initiatives could help mitigate the risk of developing T2DM in these populations.

A study examined the determinants of glucose imbalance and its impact on developing undiagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in urban and rural communities in Ghana. The study found significant differences between urban and rural areas. Urban residents exhibited higher rates of overweight/obesity ($p < 0.05$) and unhealthy dietary practices ($p < 0.05$), which were major contributors to glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM. The study emphasized the need for lifestyle interventions tailored to urban settings to mitigate these risks [6].

A related study focused on the prevalence and associated risk factors of undiagnosed T2DM in urban and rural areas of Ghana. The research highlighted that urban residents had a significantly higher prevalence of undiagnosed T2DM compared to rural dwellers ($p < 0.05$). Key risk factors included lack of physical activity, obesity, and poor dietary habits, with urban residents showing higher incidences of these factors [7].

A study investigated the increasing prevalence of T2DM and the impact of ethnicity in Northern Sudan. The study found that urban residence (AOR 1.23, 95% CI 1.09-1.41), age above 60 years (AOR 4.77, 95% CI 4.04-5.63), and obesity (AOR 1.26, 95% CI 1.03-1.55) were significant risk factors. Ethnicity also played a crucial role, with individuals of Egyptian descent having a higher risk (AOR 1.28, 95% CI 1.04-1.57) [8].

A systematic review of environmental risk factors for T2DM was conducted. The review identified walkability, air pollution, food and physical activity environments, and roadways proximity as key environmental determinants. Higher levels of walkability and green space were associated with lower T2DM risk, while increased noise and air pollution were linked to higher risk ($p < 0.01$). The study called for further investigation using longitudinal studies to establish causal relationships [9].

A study assessed the 10-year risk of developing T2DM in rural communities in Southern Nigeria using the Finnish Diabetes Risk Score (FINDRISC). The study found that 41% of participants had a low risk of developing T2DM,

with significant positive correlations between Total Diabetes Risk Score (TDRS) and Random Blood Glucose (RBG) levels among males ($r = 0.315$, $p = 0.001$). The study highlighted the lower propensity of rural dwellers to develop T2DM compared to urban residents [10].

Another study explored the role of postprandial endotoxemia in promoting inflammation-induced insulin resistance and its influence on T2DM development. The study found that patients with higher postprandial endotoxemia levels had a significantly increased risk of developing T2DM (HR 2.076, 95% CI 1.149-3.750). The combination of high endotoxemia levels and the FINDRISC score provided a better risk assessment (HR 3.835, 95% CI 1.323-11.114) [11].

Conclusion

The study found that glucose imbalance and undiagnosed T2DM were prevalent in both urban and rural communities, with a higher prevalence observed in the rural community. Significant determinants of glucose imbalance included age, BMI, and low socio-economic status. The results underscore the importance of targeted interventions to address glucose imbalance and prevent the development of T2DM, particularly in rural areas with lower socio-economic status.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Targeted interventions are needed to address glucose imbalance and prevent T2DM, especially in rural areas with lower socio-economic status. Public health initiatives should focus on lifestyle modifications and improving access to healthcare services.

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